

Introduction: Understanding the compressional behaviour of the Moon’s regolith is fundamental to comprehending the surfaces development over time. In the context of our work, the turnover pressure is a measure for the transition from loose, weak bounded surface material to denser deeper material due to hydrostatic pressure [1], which can be measured experimentally. This study aims to derive the turnover pressure as a function of the regolith grain size, allowing to define the stratigraphic profile of the regolith in terms of the volume filling factor [1]. The understanding of this relation is crucial to sufficiently constrain mechanical and physical properties like the thermal conductivity [2].

Previous work: The turnover pressure was introduced in the prescription of [3] as

$$\phi(p) = \phi_2 - \frac{\phi_2 - \phi_1}{\exp\left[\frac{\log(p) - \log(p_m)}{\Delta}\right] + 1}$$

with ϕ_1 being the volume filling factor before compression, ϕ_2 being the volume filling factor at maximum compression, Δ is a measure of the exponential width and p_m defines the centre point between ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 . The steepness of the transition is the greatest at p_m . The relation between the turnover pressure p_m and the grain size r is often described as a power law

$$p_m(r) \propto r^\alpha$$

where the value for the power α is debated as $\alpha = 4/3$ [1] or $\alpha = 2$ [4]. Both relations were derived by describing the development of the volume filling factor with mechanical properties of the sampled grains [1, 4]. Figure 1 visualises the clear differences in regard of the two proposed dependencies. It should be noted, that the experimental work of [1] used $r > 5 \mu\text{m}$ only and the model of [4] grains with $r < 5 \mu\text{m}$ mostly. Therefore, the relation might potentially not be described by one slope but a gradual transition depending on r (J. Blum, pers. comm.). Figure 1 also shows a clear lack of available data and a significant uncertainty in measured values of p_m .

Figure 1: Slopes of proposed dependency with slopes $\alpha = 4/3$ [1] and $\alpha = 2$ [4]. The relations are fitted to the measurement of [3, circle] in blue and to the measurement of [1, square] with $r = 500 \mu\text{m}$ in red. (modified after Figure 2 of [5])

Experiment: To obtain more and accurate measurements, a similar approach to the omnidirectional compression experiment of [3] will be used. A dust sample with a diameter of 20 mm and a height of max. 10 mm to avoid the Janssen effect [6, 7] will be omnidirectionally compressed by a piston within a borehole inside a cylinder. The dust samples will vary in shape and in grain size distribution. The design will allow a precise measurement of the compression displacement via distance sensors. Initially, the sample will be compressed by weights and the exerted pressure determined with an underlying scale. In a subsequent step the piston will be connected to a force sensor which will be connected to a motor to more precisely measure the exerted force and therefore pressure. Finally, the experiment will be conducted in a vacuum chamber, eliminating measurement deviations due to atmospheric influences like moisture within the sample and air pressure. The resulting data will help to determine a detailed relation between p_m and r and constrain the mechanical and physical properties of the regolith.

References:

- [1] Schräpler R. et al. (2015) *Icarus*, 257, 33-46.
- [2] Bürger J. et al. (2024) *JGR: Planets*, 129(3), e2023JE008152.
- [3] Güttler C. et al. (2009) *The Astrophysical Journal*, 701(1), 130-141.
- [4] Tatsuuma M. et al. (2023) *The Astrophysical Journal*, 953(1), 6.
- [5] Bürger J. et al. (unpublished, pers. comm.), corrigendum on [2].
- [6] Janssen, H. A. (1895) *Zeitschr. d.Vereines deutscher Ingenieure*, 39, 1045.
- [7] Sperl M. (2006) *Granular Matter*, 8(2), 59-65.